

OPPORTUNITIES FOR STRUCTURING REGIONAL BUSINESS AND UTILITY SYSTEMS IN MUNICIPALITIES**Nikolay Tsonkov***Associate Professor**University of National and World Economy (UNWE)**Bulgaria, 1700 Sofia, "Studentski" str. "8th December" № 19***Abstract**

The development of regions is at the heart of any country's economic prosperity. Viewed in this way, it can be assumed that economic development represents the totality of the territorial development of all regions. In this regard, it is important to identify and examine the primary factors generating growth and regional development. Some main drivers of regional growth are national and local policies, the business environment formed, regional incentives for entrepreneurship, and the state of the natural, demographic, and economic systems. Regional business and entrepreneurship are significant drivers in achieving regional sustainable and territorial development. The main objective of this report is to analyze regional business through the formation of a local business ecosystem based on the utility system of municipalities.

Keywords. regional development, regional policy, municipalities, territorial community, regional sustainable development, regional deconcentration, utility system

Introduction

In the modern market system and capitalism, business is a key element and driver of economic development. In this sense, the development of regions and markets depends on several factors such as political decisions and policies implemented, state governance, the environment for doing business, the legislative ecosystem, municipalities and the environment they form, the size and demographic structure of the population, purchasing power, the existing potential of the economic system and many others. Of course, in the context of globalization and openness of national economies, an important factor for business development at all levels is the international and national conjuncture, and in this sense the economic and business cycles that determine business development opportunities. In this regard, we can point to the instruments of institutional economics and market incentives, which, depending on the stage of the economic and business cycle, can stagnate or stimulate the development of the economy and business, respectively.

Methodological aspects of the research

The author assumes that the local business environment is formed by several factors, with the utility system of municipalities determining its development. The state of the local business environment determines the dynamics of regional entrepreneurship and the development and structuring of regional business. National (regional) and local policies are important in this

direction. In this regard, the main objective is to analyze and highlight the opportunities for structuring and regional business development based on national and local policies, including the utilities system developed by municipalities. The research is realized through the territorial and network approaches use which are complemented by analytical, descriptive, horological methods, factor, and situational analysis.

Theoretical framework

The analysis of the scientific literature reveals two main conceptual strands. One comprises authors who study regional entrepreneurship and the impact of the business environment on its dynamics. [1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6] The other strand focuses on research related to the definition of regional business, the elucidation of regional business cycles and the nature and factors influencing the economic development of regions. [7, 8, 9, 10, 11]

Relevant to this study is the analysis of Guo, C Liu, Q Xie, and X Lin, who propose a model for assessing economic development at the national and regional levels. [12] Using their proposed model, the interrelationships among the factors that affect the economic development of regions can be analyzed (Fig. 1). The author adopts the proposed schematic expression of the factor conditioning of business environment, entrepreneurship factors, economic activity, natural conditions and resources, policy pursued, and many others.

includes the economic actors, the market (population), and its governance.

Fig. 2. Schematic expression of regional level inter-linkages in the context of regional development. Ex. Tsonkov, N., 2023.

The state and the administrative-territorial units (municipalities) influence the territory and the population (territorial communities) through local and regional policies. As a result of the policies implemented, the utility and efficiency of utility systems are shaping the regional environment. This local ecosystem changes in socio-economic terms, which is expressed in the process of territorial (regional) development (Figure 2). [17] The concept of "regional policy" is per-

ceived as: "a system of normatively regulated documents and instruments aimed at the realization of regional development objectives in administrative-territorial units" (Article 4 of the Law on Regional Development). [18]

Regional policy or regional development policy supports and complements the utility systems of municipalities, as well as the implemented local initiatives and measures to improve the population's living conditions and stimulate regional business (Fig. 3) [17]

Fig. 3. Role of the municipality for territorial and regional development. Ex. Tsonkov, N. 2023.

Regional business is the formation of specific local socio-economic conditions, organizing and carrying out various types of economic activity for profit and to meet the needs of the local community, which together with other economic activities form the regional economy of a particular territory or municipality. That is to say, a regional business is the aggregate of all economic activities carried out within a regional economy that are distinctly regional and local. Regional businesses therefore interact with local communities on an ongoing basis. We could point to several examples of regional business. Typically these are activities that primarily serve the local population, including the wholesale and retail production and distribution of goods and food. Prominent examples of regional businesses are bakeries, which typically supply bread to the local market. Other examples are grocery stores, especially small neighborhood stores. Based on these examples, it is clear that regional businesses are mainly formed by micro, small, and less often medium-sized firms that tend to rely on local markets and cater to the needs of local communities.

On the other hand, regional businesses are strongly influenced by the local environment. The regional environment should be seen as the shaping of specific conditions based on local and national policies.

To the specific conditions, we can include - local communities, features, nature, resources, political and legislative environment, economic situation, etc. The municipality, which provides the so-called basic services to the population (the local territorial community), is of great importance in shaping the regional environment. These services include utilities and public works, and services such as property management, transport, municipal waste, environmental infrastructure, green spaces and building stock, water supply, sewerage, electricity, gas supply, housing, urban planning, etc. The services and activities have a significant impact on the development of the territory of each municipality. The basic necessary conditions for the normal course of economic and demographic reproduction processes are developed. Through territory planning and organizing activities and infrastructure construction. At the same time, the last decades of transition have changed the nature and appearance of Bulgarian cities.

In broader macroeconomic terms, the concept of utility means the satisfaction of a person from the use of a good or the use of services. [19] The concept was first introduced by I. Bentham. [20] And here we see an intersection between the utility system and regional business because a purely economic product or service is useful when it achieves a certain level of satisfaction from its consumption. In this sense, we could speak of

expected and subjective utility (utility). In this way, we can define the expected utility outcome of public works and public utilities (the utility system of municipalities), which is expressed in better socio-economic conditions and increased attractiveness of the municipality.

Therefore, we can conclude that the utility system of the municipality is the set of public works and utilities that form the necessary basic conditions of the population and business for the normal reproduction of the specific territory, and satisfy their most important needs. In this sense, the utility system of activities and services (referred to as the utility system for short) is closely linked to the utility of the activities and services

provided by the municipality. The needs that the municipality satisfies for the normal functioning of socio-economic processes in a specific territory are expressed by the degree of utility in the functioning of the municipality.

In Bulgaria, the state of the utilities system, and therefore the opportunities for structuring regional business, is at a very unsatisfactory level. As it is clear from Figure 4 the main problems in municipalities are demographic, economic, administrative, and infrastructural. [17] All this points to a non-functioning regional ecosystem, including the utility system of activities and services.

Fig. 4. The most significant problems in the Bulgarian municipalities. Ex. Author's research. Tsonkov, N., 2022.

Municipalities have an important place for regional development in Bulgaria which should form a favorable local business ecosystem. Therefore, the de-

gree to which the utility system is established, complemented, and reinforced by regional and local policies, is very important.

Fig. 5. Evaluation of the utility system by businesses and citizens. Ex. Author's research. Ex. Tsonkov, N. 2023.

From the author's research, it seems that businesses and citizens do not highly value the utility services and activities offered and provided (Figure 5). [17] Therefore, the role of the municipality and the state is to strengthen and develop the utility system and thus form a favorable environment for regional business, leading to regional sustainable and territorial development of the regions in Bulgaria. In a broader context, it is noted that as a result of the different conditions and basic services provided by municipalities, there are

deep regional disparities in the Bulgarian state in territorial terms. [21] Therefore, it is necessary to think in the direction of developing and implementing a uniform standard of utility system of municipalities, to be guaranteed by the state budget through the subsidies received. this governance process requires the continuation of the decentralization process and autonomy of local government in Bulgaria.

Conclusion

In this study, the author attempted to analyze the theoretical aspects of regional business and the utilities system. On the one hand, regional business contributes to the socio-economic development of the territorial community and locality. On the other hand, with the implementation of regional and local policies, the local community and regional businesses are guaranteed to form the necessary conditions for reproduction and development through the utility services provision and the performance of activities that improve the quality of life and business development. The author's research shows that municipalities and the state do not provide the necessary basic conditions for the territorial communities development and regional businesses. Therefore, there is a need for targeted impact on territories through the formulation and implementation of effective regional and local policies.

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